

PROVERBS WITH THE SOMATIC COMPONENT *MOUTH/OG'IZ* IN TWO LANGUAGES

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola o'zbek va ingliz maqollarida "og'iz" somatizmining qo'llanilishi orqali nutq, xulq-atvor va donolik haqidagi madaniy tasavvurlarni o'rganadi. Ularni taqqoslash orqali o'zbek maqollari ko'pincha so'zlarda ehtiyotkor bo'lish va sukut saqlashga urg'u berishini, ingliz maqollari esa mas'uliyat va so'zlarni amallar bilan muvofiqlashtirishga e'tibor qaratishini ko'rsatadi. Maqola ikkala madaniyatning ham "og'iz" obrazidan odamlarning qanday gapirishi va harakat qilishi kerakligini o'rgatish uchun qanday foydalanishini tushunishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Somatizm, og'iz, o'zbek maqollari, ingliz maqollari, madaniy qadriyatlar, nutq, xulq-atvor, og'zaki ehtiyotkorlik, mas'uliyat, qiyosiy tahlil.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье исследуются культурные представления о речи, поведении и мудрости посредством использования соматизма «рот» в узбекских и английских пословицах. Сравнивая их, можно увидеть, что в узбекских пословицах часто подчеркивается осторожность в словах и молчание, тогда как в английских пословицах подчеркивается ответственность и соответствие слов действиям. Статья помогает понять, как обе культуры используют образ «рта», чтобы научить людей говорить и действовать.

Ключевые слова: соматизм, рот, узбекские пословицы, английские пословицы, культурные ценности, речь, поведение, словесное предостережение, ответственность, сравнительный анализ.

ANNOTATION

This article looks at how the "mouth" is used in Uzbek and English proverbs to show cultural ideas about speech, behavior, and wisdom. By comparing the two, it shows that Uzbek proverbs often focus on being careful with words and staying quiet, while English proverbs stress responsibility and matching actions with words. The paper helps us understand how both cultures use the "mouth" as a symbol to teach lessons about how people should speak and act.

Key words: Somatism, mouth, Uzbek proverbs, English proverbs, cultural values, speech, behavior, verbal restraint, accountability, comparative analysis.

INTRODUCTION

In both Uzbek and English cultures, proverbs serve as valuable reflections of societal wisdom and moral teachings, often utilizing somatic imagery, such as the "mouth," to convey deeper meanings. The mouth, an essential part of the body involved in eating, speaking, and expressing oneself, appears frequently in proverbs from both languages. While in English proverbs, the mouth often symbolizes accountability and the importance of aligning words with actions, Uzbek proverbs emphasize verbal restraint and caution. This contrast highlights not only linguistic nuances but also cultural values regarding speech, behavior, and personal conduct. Through the exploration of proverbs featuring the "mouth," we gain insights into how these two languages use similar somatic imagery to teach lessons on wisdom, restraint, and human interaction[4; p.89].

MAIN PART

The mouth is the cavity between the two jaws, serving the purposes of eating, speaking, or producing sound. The somatism of the mouth is more commonly found in Uzbek proverbs compared to English, and in both languages, this somatism often emphasizes the importance of keeping one's mouth shut and being cautious. Through the analysis of English proverbs: "Put your money where your mouth is." This proverb uses the images of "mouth" and "money." It reminds people that they must back up their words with action. In other words, if you're making a claim or supporting something, you should contribute to it with resources or funds. This proverb highlights the necessity of taking responsibility and aligning words with actions. "Out of the mouths of babes come gems." In this proverb, the images of "babies" (young children) and "gems" represent the idea that wisdom and truth can come from unexpected places. It shows that sometimes the simple words of children or inexperienced people may carry deep wisdom or truth. It suggests that seemingly simple or innocent statements can express great wisdom. "A full purse makes the mouth run over." This proverb, with the images of a "full purse" and a "talking mouth," conveys the connection between wealth and behavior. It means that as wealth increases, people are more likely to talk more, show off, or boast. It highlights how acquiring wealth can change one's behavior, sometimes leading to excessive speech. "Keep your purse and your mouth closed."

This proverb uses the images of a "purse" and a "mouth" to symbolize caution, modesty, and the avoidance of excessive talk[1;p.49]. It advises people to be financially and verbally cautious. Instead of spending money or talking unnecessarily, the proverb reminds people to remain modest and attentive in personal matters. "If you keep your mouth shut, you won't put your foot in it." In this proverb, the images of "keeping your mouth shut" and "putting your foot in it" represent caution and avoiding saying the wrong thing. The proverb suggests that if a person refrains from speaking unnecessarily or carelessly, they will not find themselves in awkward or embarrassing situations.

Uzbek proverbs with somatic components: "Yopiq og'izga pashsha tushmas."

This proverb advises caution and avoiding unnecessary talk. The "closed mouth" symbolizes a cautious and self-restrained person, while "won't attract flies" indicates that negative consequences, problems, or unpleasant situations will not arise. The proverb emphasizes that those who avoid excessive or unnecessary speech will protect themselves from uncomfortable situations and mistakes. **"Og'ziga kelganni demak-nodoning ishi, Oldiga kelganni yemak-hayvonning ishi."** This proverb stresses the importance of verbal caution and speaking thoughtfully. **"Og'zida kumush qoshiq bilan tu'g'ulmoq"**, represents thoughtless speech, or a lack of wisdom, while "eating whatever is placed in front of you" reflects acting based on instinct, like an animal. The proverb encourages people to choose their words carefully and not act on animalistic instincts, reminding us to preserve human intellect and moral values. "Born with a silver spoon in their mouth." This proverb expresses the idea of being born into wealth or comfortable circumstances. The phrase "born with a silver spoon" describes a person who is surrounded by wealth, luxury, or comfort from birth. The proverb reminds us that some people's success or opportunities in life are connected to the family and circumstances they were born into. "A fool will lose what's in their mouth." This proverb uses the image of a "fool" to describe a person who cannot control themselves and speaks excessively. "Will lose what's in their mouth" means they will create problems for themselves because of what they say. The proverb warns that those who

speak thoughtlessly may ultimately suffer or find themselves in an unpleasant situation [5;p.71].

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the use of the "mouth" in Uzbek and English proverbs reflects different cultural perspectives on speech and behavior. Uzbek proverbs emphasize the importance of caution and restraint in communication, while English proverbs highlight the need for accountability and the alignment of words with actions. Despite these differences, both languages use the image of the "mouth" to convey important moral lessons, showing how a simple somatic symbol can carry deep cultural significance.

REFERENCES:

1. Wardhaugh R. Investigating Language. Central Problems in Linguistics. – Oxford: Blackwell, 1994. – 292 p.
2. Yusupov O'. Ingliz tili grammatikasidan universal qo'llanma. – T.: Akademnashr, 2011. – 37 b.
3. Абдуллаев Ж. Ҳозирги ўзбек адабий тили (синтаксис). Қўшма гап. – Гулистон, 2008. – 143 б.
4. Абдурахмонов Ф. Ўзбек тили грамматикаси (Синтаксис). – Тошкент: Ўқитувчи, 1996. – 247 б.
5. Юсупов У. Инглиз ва ўзбек тилларининг чоғиштирма лингвистикаси. – Тошкент: Академнашр, 2013. – 282 б.
6. Уралова О.П. Инглиз ва ўзбек тилларида “оила” бош лексемали мақоллар семантикаси ва структураси. Филол.фанлари бўйича фалсафа докт. (PhD) дисс. автореферати. – Самарқанд, 2020. – 58 б.